

Innovation, the Relation between Innovation Strategies and Organizational Performance: A Research on Footwear Sector in Konya

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Abstract: In this study followings are examined: innovation, organizational performance and three main innovation strategies, namely aggressive, defensive and imitative and dependent strategies. The research employed survey method to small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) working in the field of footwear in Konya. The main aim is to examine innovation levels and strategies and to determine the relation among innovation, innovation strategies and organizational performance of enterprises working in the field of footwear in Konya. Following this aim, it has been found out that the level of innovation and organizational performance of organizations with aggressive innovation strategies show a difference and there is a positive and meaningful statistical relation between innovation and innovation strategies and organizational performance.

Keywords: Innovation, Innovation Strategies, Business Performance, Footwear Sector.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the globalizing competence environment in which scientific and technological developments occur rapidly, organizations - as being open-systems- should adapt to changes occurring in their environments. In the process of adaptation, not only outer factors such as economic developments, social trends, international trade standardizations but also inner elements such as growth, mergers, decrease in sales, change of management, organizational insufficiency etc. make change a must. In this point, organizations should react these changes by taking into consideration both inner and outer environment dynamics.

These experienced changes force organizations to make innovations and develop strategies to manage these innovation activities. In this content, organizational performance that is the most important factor in sustaining of organizations' regularity holds a key role. So, in this study innovation, innovation strategies and organizational

performance terms are discussed and the results of the research done in footwear sector in Konya are given.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

After information is given about innovation term, innovation strategies and organizational performance, the research and its results will be given.

2.1. INNOVATION TERM AND ITS DEFINITION

Innovation is a strong competition tool in organizations' having competition superiority, increasing of profits and cash flow and being one step forward from others in the sector. Innovation can be described as a newly accepted idea, application or object by an individual or another apply unit (Tekin et al., 2003: 139).

Although there are many definitions of innovation term, we can say that some of them are similar and some others indicate to different parts of the term. Innovation is a common aptitude that enables organizations to foresee and form a vision. Besides, innovation is the series of values that allow feeling, anticipating an emotional situation and beyond the current time. Innovation is not only a new idea but also the process of converting a new idea to a commercializing product (Durna, 2002: 5-6).

In the literature, there are two different approaches related to the definition of innovation. It is sometimes described as a "thing" (the first presentation of a product in a market or area) and sometimes as a "process" (the process of creating and inventing a new product). According to Rogers, innovation is described as ideas, applications and objects that are perceived as new by individuals or other units adopting them. Dos describes innovation as adopting and commercializing a new product, method or organizational structure via researching, inventing, trying, improving or imitating (Oğuztürk, 2003: 254). Innovation, in another definition, is described as realization of a new or highly improved product (goods or services) or process in inner-organization applications, organization of the work place or outer relations, a new marketing method or a new organizational method (Gökçe, 2010: 1).

Innovation is described also as both a process and a result. As a process, innovation refers to a special situation of an organizational change and activities done in order to produce a new product. As a result, it refers to new or improved products and services gained as a result of innovation activities (Naktiyok, 2007: 213; Schermerhon, 2007: 333; Narayanan, 2001: 68).

Drucker (1998: 30-31) describes innovation as useful information that gives a chance for the first time to people that have different knowledge and skills and work in an organization in order to make them productive. What is more, innovation is a special tool of entrepreneurship and an action that introduces the sources which create a new capacity in order to generate welfare.

2.2. INNOVATION STRATEGIES

Innovation strategies consist of financial aims related to a new product or service and growth fields. They are also strategic roles that describe the strategic missions of new products or services and complement of criteria that provide

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series of filters from which ideas of new products and services should pass (Sarı ve Işık, 2011: 546). In the literature, innovation strategies are generally dealt with under three sub-titles as aggressive, defensive, imitative and dependent.

2.2.1. Aggressive Strategy

It is the strategy that aims to develop product and process innovations and as a result of this experiencing the benefits of being the first in an existing market (Aygen, 2007: 45). Aggressive innovation strategy is designed in order to take technical and market leadership by developing new products and being one step forward from the competitors (Durna, 2002:129). An entrepreneur who uses aggressive strategy wants to be the first that takes the benefit of innovation and get an important competition advantage (Durna, 2002:130).

2.2.2. Defensive Strategy

It is the strategy that generally avoids taking the risk which is a result of being the first in the market and consists of works relying on taking the benefits of opportunities created by organizations that are first in the market (Aygen, 2007: 47). Innovators with defensive strategies do not want to be the first in the world, but they do not want to fall behind in the technical changes either. They do not intend to face the high risk of being first and they hope to benefit from first entrepreneurs' mistakes and the market opened by them (Durna, 2002: 134).

Like organizations with aggressive strategies, such organizations also have Research & Development (R&D) activities. However, these activities follow the leader and aim to solve problems and they are related to applications. These R&D activities that intend to examine the products of first organizations in the market and make up their deficiencies or differentiate them have less cost and risks (Aygen, 2007: 47).

2.2.3. Imitative and Dependent Strategy

Organizations with this strategy are not in the first position in the market; they avoid taking risks and have low costs, materials and labor force. Such organizations, different from organizations with other two strategies, do not allocate resources to R&D. The thing important for them is to apply scientific and technical information of the organizations they imitate and choose the organization that is prior in the current market (Aygen, 2007: 48). Imitative organizations follow innovative ones; they prefer to work with low labor force, materials, and energy and investment costs; not much source is assigned to R&D in such organizations. It is a strategy that relies on benefiting from leader organization's products via license etc. instead of investing to innovation activities. So, organizations with this strategy do not generally have the triumph technology in the market (Güleş and Bülbül, 2004: 177).

2.2.4. Dependent Strategy

It is a strategy that accepts to depend on powerful organizations in terms of innovations. The organizations that follow this strategy do not attempt to make a change or

imitate the products they produce. They make technical changes in their products due to demands by customers or dependent organizations (Güleş and Bülbül, 2004: 177).

2.2.5. Traditional Strategy

It is a strategy that depends on occupational abilities rather than scientific studies. No change occurs until there is a demand by the market or a requirement caused by competition (Güleş and Bülbül, 2004: 177).

Traditional strategy mentions three alternative types of competition. First is management efficiency which generally means organization's cost and quality competition; the second is called developing new product and shows organization's production competition, and the third is target competition that is the market target (Aygen, 2007: 49).

2.2.6. Following Opportunities Strategy

It is a strategy that relies on finding weaknesses of the competitors and undiscovered parts of the market. Organizations with this strategy are outward-looking and continuously look for new market opportunities. They benefit from opportunities that the leader does not see or has left empty in the markets which change rapidly while not facing with the leader (Güleş and Bülbül, 2004: 178). This strategy can be said to be similar with military strategy. In order organizations to follow this strategy successfully, they need to see the opportunities in the market before others via a powerful communication network, to be the one that is aware of new ideas with a big potential and benefit from opportunities ignored by big in wide markets competitors (İraz, 2010: 103).

2.2.7. Attainment Strategy

This strategy includes innovation as a result of applying of information related to a given technological innovation within the organization. So, an opportunity arises to benefit from a technological innovation produced as a result of R&D investments in another organization with a considerably low cost (Zerenler et al., 2007:664). Organizations following this strategy attain the technological innovation or people or organizations that have it (İraz, 2010: 103).

2.3. ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

One of the most important problems faced in organizations today is to determine to what extent missions given to workers are fulfilled or what their service capacity capabilities are. This problem has especially caused the term organizational performance become rapidly important in organizations (Bayram, 2006: 47).

There are many definitions in the literature related to performance term. It can be described as evaluating of all efforts for realizing organization aims. Performance, in other words, is quantitative and qualitative expression of what an individual, group or organization that works can provide related to aims of that work (Çalık, 2003: 9). Performance term shows where a working individual, group, unit or

organization has reached via that work according to the aim (Argon and Eren, 2004: 224).

Organizational performance can be expressed as evaluation of all efforts for realizing organization aims. In other words, it can be described as expression of the realization level of the organization' aim or mission by looking at outcomes or results of a given term.

Evaluation of organizational performance is a requirement because of both controlling the organization of its own efforts and creating customer satisfaction in the target market. Besides, performance evaluation creates decision inputs that direct organization managers' decisions (Turunç, 2006: 131; Yıldız, 2010: 180). Performance evaluation prevents the organization standing by against changes in or out of the organization; it provides to take an active role in being able to react those changes, looking for their reasons etc. There are some benefits of measuring organizational performance: it enables to see how the organization operates, provides valuable information to organizations in determining the sources of their problems and main reasons that lie behind their success and/or failure, enables to determine prospective performance deficits, shows to what extent the predetermined use of resources have been realized and it is also effective in determining the performance to be awarded.

As a result, organizations use many performance criteria in order to evaluate previous activities and take strategic decisions. Undoubtedly, all these dimensions of performance have important effects on organizational performance (Erdem et al., 2011: 84-85). In this study, the effect of institutionalization that is one of the mentioned dimensions on innovation and organizational performance has been examined.

3. EXAMINATION OF INNOVATION AND THE RELATION BETWEEN INNOVATION STRATEGIES AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

3.1. Data Collection Method

This study that aims to determine innovation levels and strategies and examine the relations between innovation strategies and organizational performance of small and medium sized (SMEs) organizations in the footwear sector in Konya employed survey method. Data gained via convenience sampling examined by using SPSS 16.0 program.

3.2. Aims and Hypothesis of the Research

The aim of the study is to determine innovation levels and strategies of small and medium sized (SMEs) organizations working in footwear sector in Konya and to examine the relations between innovation, innovation strategies and organizational performance. The sample of the research includes small and medium sized (SMS) organizations working in footwear sector in Konya. It has been found out that there are 1100 organizations in this sector and 110 of them are small and medium sized. The survey was given to 80 of them. By this aim, developed hypothesis are as follows:

H₁: There is a meaningful difference in organizations' innovation strategies according to their innovation levels.

H₂: There is a meaningful difference between organizations' organizational performance and innovation strategies.

H₃: There is a meaningful difference between organizations' innovation levels and innovation strategies.

H₄: There is a meaningful difference between organizations' innovation levels and organizational performance.

H₅: There is a meaningful difference between organizations' innovation strategies and organizational performance.

3.3. Scales Used in the Research

The research relies on "Innovation Scale" developed by Calantone et al. (2000) in order to determine organizations' levels of institutionalization and innovation and study by Örucü et al. (2002) in order to find out their innovation strategies; and "Organizational Performance Scale" by Calantone et al. (2002) has been used to find out organizations' performances.

3.4. Analysis and Findings

A survey was carried out to the managers of small and medium sized (SMEs) organizations working in footwear sector in Konya in order to find out the effects of institutionalization and innovation levels on organizational performance. Demographic information about the managers that took the survey is given in Table-1:

Product / service innovation is of great importance for the firm and the industry as well as the economy. Such innovations will tend to increase the demand for labor and employment because they will lead to an increase in the production by developing markets for new products / services or increasing the demand for improved products / services (Taymaz, 2003).

Product innovation is important for increasing the power of competitiveness of enterprises and enhancing the sustainability in the market (John, 1999; 6). New products can be made with small adaptations to existing products or by creating an entirely different line of new products. New products and services in general have been designed to reduce the market share by leaving behind other businesses, but at the same time they have also been designed to gain customers, a new market and expand the market (Aygen, 2006).

3.2 Process Innovation

It is to apply New or significantly improved production or distribution method. It may include the changes in the production or distribution technique, technical equipment or software. Process innovation aims to reduce the unit costs of production or distribution costs (Kiwari, 2008).

In terms of production and service process can be specified as a series of activities done in order to accept raw materials, energy, information as input and conversion of them to output such as product or service. Process

innovation can be expressed as to apply radical new methods in order to increase the performance of business processes (Papinniemi, 1999, 96).

The reason behind the process innovation is to enhance efficiency and productivity. Technological advances and investments are usually the basis of the idea of process innovation (Hjalager, 2010).

Although process innovation is an innovation type which can be done alone or sustained, it maintains its connection with other types of innovations and it is associated with them as well. Customer perception, which is a requirement of competitive environment and the most important aspects of innovation, and knowledge exchange level, makes process innovation affect other types of innovation and take an important role. In this context, process innovation can be perceived as radical improvement of the basic business processes through the use of new tools and business designs and revealing businesses' process view (Güleş and Bülbül, 2004; 43).

3.3 Marketing Innovation

Marketing innovation is to use new marketing methods with spectacular changes in product design, packaging, distribution or pricing. Marketing innovation aims to shift customer needs to the newly opened market or shift into a new position, of course, with the objective of increasing the firm's sales (Kiwari, 2008).

Marketing innovation should be monitored in three stages. These are explore, development and distribution. In the explore stage, the problems of the target group should be determined and the recommendations should be identified. In the development stage, solutions and tools should be developed for known and explored problems. In the distribution stage, it is needed to ensure that distribution is not an instant but constant business and its continuation should be provided (Henriksen and Skou, 2005).

The final aim of marketing innovation is to increase sales. As related to this aim, there exist the aims of fulfilling customer needs more successfully, creating new markets and replacing organization's product to a new form in the market. In the context of organization's market share and competition superiority or being able to compete, it wouldn't be wrong to accept keeping organization's current status and keeping its profitableness level fixed or improving it as parallel to this within the aims of marketing innovation (Şahin, 2009).

3.4 Organizational Innovation

Organizational innovation is developing new ways of working and fulfilling services or adapting existing methods to organization conditions (Elçi, 2007).

Organizational and process innovations cause some uncertain situations in innovation searches as they are similar to each other. Because of this, if the innovation involves new or largely improved production or supply methods that are foreseen to decrease cost per unit or improve production quality, this is a process innovation. However, if it includes first use of new organizational methods in its trade applications, workplace organizations or external relations, this is an organizational innovation. If the

innovation involves both of the above, then it is both process and organizational innovation (Oslo Guide, 2005:59).

3. INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN SMALL AND MIDDLE SIZED ENTERPRISES (SME)

SMEs that are one of the dynamic and leading elements of the economy hold great importance in the point of countries' socio-economic development. In general, SMEs can be defined as financial enterprises that work mostly with handwork besides low capital use and have the ability to decide quickly, work with low management costs and produce cheap goods (Akgemci, 2001; 5).

Most of the SMEs can carry out those functions that big enterprises cannot do. Especially, big sized enterprises' turning into a loss maker form as a result of the difficulty they experience in adopting new changes and developments in communication and production technology has changed the idea that they are the "engines of the economic development" gradually; "reduction" that includes the main dynamic of the change inside has come into prominent. In this point, SMEs have functioned as a safety valve in crisis times when market shortage have risen, demand has fallen, energy and raw material straits have been experienced in the world economy thanks to their energetic, flexible, multiple production and service forms, and they have become an indispensable part of industrial structure especially in the point of sustaining competition in international markets (Bayrak and Akdiş, 2000).

It is possible to explain SMEs' most important features as follows: first of all, they are more independent than big enterprises. There is not a pressure on the enterprise from shareholders, board of management or credit providers, because the enterprise is run by its owner and with equity capital. Secondly, attempt and entity abilities in SMEs are much. These enterprises are the results of attempts, not long established family enterprises. Thirdly, personal relations are in the foreground in SMEs. Relations both with workers and customers and suppliers out of the enterprise show personal (Özdemir and Karaca, 2007; 3)

SMEs' working close to the consumers in all levels provides them with the opportunity to make required changes in production mechanisms shortly after evaluating consumers' choices and problems and increases their ability to adapt changing market conditions quickly. For this reason, SMEs are staler to innovation as their high level of reaction and flexibility against the changes in the environment. So, SMEs has gradually become the source of new ideas and inventions and contribute in providing required flexibility in the industry (İmamoğlu, 2002: 84).

SMEs can make new investments without big investments and required technology. This situation gives SMEs the chance to apply new ideas, because their ability to use their production tools in multiple ways and adaptation easiness are important advantages. SMEs are ideal environments that insure of forming new ideas and crises which happen in different forms requires taking the risk of trying new ideas (İraz, 2005: 233).

Small sized enterprises generally take support from external channels to develop innovation as they have limited sources and are focused on a specific area. As SMEs are considerably small when compared with multi-national enterprises, they might show avoidance of developing

innovation. On the other hand, SMEs' contribution to the economy is highly important and they are required to be evaluated in the point of reformist perspective. SMEs cooperate with big enterprises because of some reasons such as their limited sources; big enterprises' having a R&D department but reformist applications' contributing to SMEs' markets. SMEs' contributions to innovation shows difference because of their coming from different environments and being different in the point of size (Hantal, 2008, 22).

A small and middle sized enterprise can compete with big ones via focusing its activities on developing new products and services and marketing. SMEs have the possibility to follow strategies such as entering to the markets that big enterprises can't do, adapting themselves to demand changes and even changing their production field when needed by using their superiority of flexibility instead of producing the same things with big enterprises. As a result of this, SMEs develop a wider movement area by using reforms.

This strategy tendency related to the innovation is seen clearly in the computer field that is improving especially in small and middle sized enterprises. In this point, innovations can be either radical or small and even artificial. The important thing is the market value of the innovation rather than its technical quality, because the value of an innovation in the point of an enterprise is measured by its market value; and this value is explained by the number of the customers that the innovation reaches. When SMEs are examined in this point of view, they can be said to be more innovative considering the level of adaptation to the changing conditions of market and demand in general and production and management in specific (İraz, 2005: 233).

4. AIM AND METHOD

5.1 The Aim And The Concept of The Research

Innovation has become an important term in today's conditions in which scientific and technological developments occur very rapidly because of many similar products in the market and becoming imitating of services easier. As a result of this, it has become a trend topic for both academicians and production and service providers.

In this study, it is aimed to look at innovation term from different perspectives. It has been tried to find out and present innovation tendencies of manufacturing enterprises in Konya.

Small and middle sized manufacturing enterprises in Konya have been chosen as survey area because of practicability.

5.2 Method

This study employed descriptive research method which is one of the quantitative research methods. Descriptive researches are researches that aim to present the current situation for a given topic. The most common descriptive research method in social sciences is survey research. A survey is used as a data collection tool in the study. The gained data in the research was collected via face to face meeting method which is one of the primary data collection methods, and samples were chosen by random

sampling; more explanations about the survey and the statements were given when needed.

The survey used in the research consists of two parts: the first part is for finding out participant enterprises' service age and their ideas on innovation. In the second part, questions about innovation types are asked with a five scale (1 "Never", 2 "Rarely", 3 "Sometimes", 4 "Often", 5 "Always").

5.3 The Frame of the Research

Literature review and field study were done in the study. First, literature review was done then hypothesis were put forth; and then the survey was prepared to test those hypothesis. Hasan Çeliktas' study and Oslo Guide by Tubitak were benefited from in survey development process.

5.4 Universe, Sample and Data Collection Process

The main body of the study consists of small and middle sized manufacturing enterprises in Konya. Face to face meeting method was used to apply the survey. Only 72 units of the universe provided reliable information, so this number of enterprises has been the sample of the research.

The survey was tried to be applied to the management staff of small and middle sized manufacturing enterprises in Konya.

5.5 The Evaluation of the Data

Survey data was transferred to SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences, version 15.0), and a part of the analysis was done via this program.

5.6 Hypothesis of the Research

In this research, answer were tried to be found to the following questions: do enterprises give enough importance to the innovation? Is there a relationship between innovation and manufacturing enterprises' service age? What type of innovation is more common in such enterprises?

The followings are our question sentences and hypothesis to be tested:

Problem 1: Do manufacturing enterprises give importance to the innovation?

H₀: They do not give importance to the innovation.

H₁: They give importance to the innovation.

Problem 2: Is there a meaningful relationship between innovation and manufacturing enterprises' service age?

H₀: There is not a meaningful relationship between innovation and manufacturing enterprises' service age?

H₁: There is a meaningful relationship between innovation and manufacturing enterprises' service age?

Problem 3: Is it the production/service innovation that is the prominent type of innovation in manufacturing enterprises?

H₀: It is not the production/service innovation that is the prominent type of innovation in manufacturing enterprises?

H₁: It is the production/service innovation that is the prominent type of innovation in manufacturing enterprises.

5. FINDINGS AND COMMENTS

A hundred surveys were sent to the small and middle sized manufacturing enterprises in Konya; 82 of them were sent back; however, 72 were taken into evaluation. Croanbach Alpha values of all proposals were calculated and value is measured as %93 for this study. As this value is above %70, the survey can be said to be reliable.

6.1 Findings Related to Service Age of the Enterprise

Table 1 Service Age of the Enterprise

Service Age	Frequency	Percent
1-5 years	10	13,8
6-10 years	42	58,3
11-15 years	6	8,3
16-20 years	10	13,8
Above 20 years	4	5,6
Total	72	100,00

Table 1 Service Age of the Enterprise

We see that service age of 42 of the 72 surveyed manufacturing enterprises with a 58.3% is between 1-10 years. With 13.8% percent of there are 10 manufacturing enterprises aged between 16 and 20 years serving in Konya. However, according to our survey results, with 13.8% percent, 10 manufacturing enterprises are serving between 1-5 years. With 5.6% percent 4 enterprises stated that they are serving over 20 years and 6 enterprises stated that they are serving between 11 and 15 years.

6.2 Findings Related to the Necessity and Importance of Innovation for Enterprises

Do you think that innovation is important in manufacturing firms?	Frequency	Percent
Yes	72	100,0
No	0	0

Table 2 The Importance of Innovation For Enterprises

Do you think that innovation is necessary in manufacturing firms?	Frequency	Percent
Yes	72	100,0
No	0	0

Table 3 The Necessity of Innovation For Enterprises

72 small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises pointed out that innovation is important and

necessary that is to say with 100% percent they' preferred 'yes' option.

72 small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises in Konya, which is the sample of the study, are asked if innovation is important and necessary. They all answered yes to the question so that it indicates they find innovation necessary and important. In this case, the number 1 H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted on our problem. This data shows us innovation is cared in small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises.

6.3 Findings Related To Product / Service Innovation of Small and Medium-Sized Manufacturing Firms Located in Konya

	Frequency	Percent
Never	5	6,9
Rarely	10	13,9
Sometimes	10	13,9
Often	37	51,3
Always	10	13,9
Total	72	100,0

Table 4 Developing consumer-wise products or services

To the variable "Compared to that of existing products or services on the market, we develop products or services providing more benefits to consumers" from 72 manufacturing firms, with a 51.3% percent share 37 manufacturing enterprises replied 'often', while with 13.9% percent share 10 enterprises 'rarely', 10 'Sometimes', 10 preferred 'Always' options. 5 manufacturing enterprises gave the answer 'never' to this variable.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	7	9,7
Rarely	22	30,6
Sometimes	19	26,3
Often	12	16,7
Always	12	16,7
Total	72	100,0

Table 5 Presentation of First Samples of Product and Services In the Market

With a 30.62% percent 22 of 72 small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises in Konya are labeled the 'rarely' option of the item: 'In general, we present the first samples of the products and services we offer in the market'. With percentage share of 26.3 19 enterprises preferred the 'Sometimes' option while with a 16.7% percent 12 enterprises 'Often' and 12 gave the answer 'Always'. 7 manufacturing firms stated that they failed to provide a first sample of a product or service to the market by choosing the 'never' option.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	2	2,8
Rarely	2	2,8
Sometimes	13	18,1
Often	45	62,5
Always	10	13,9
Total	72	100,0

Table 6 Developing and Revising Available Products and Services

45 Manufacturing enterprises with a share of 62.5 percentage gave the 'often' answer to the variable 'We improve and revise our existing products and services. With a share of 18.1% there are 13 firms which said 'Sometimes,' to this variable. 10 firms preferred the 'Always' option whereas 2 preferred 'never' and 2 preferred 'rarely'.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	3	4,1
Rarely	2	2,8
Sometimes	35	48,6
Often	22	30,5
Always	10	13,9
Total	72	100,0

Table 7 Developing Product or Services Which Will Make Serious Changes In Consumers' Behaviors

35 enterprises with a share of 48.6% percent gave the 'Sometimes' the answer to the item: 'We develop products or services that will make a serious change in consumers' behaviors'. 22 manufacturing enterprises, with a share of 30.5 percentage preferred 'often' option. With a 13.9% percent 10 enterprises replied 'always'. 3 manufacturing firms selected "Never" option and 2 enterprises selected "rarely" option.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	3	4,1
Rarely	3	4,1
Sometimes	9	12,5
Often	25	34,7
Always	32	44,4
Total	72	100,0

Table 8 Always Adding New Ones to Existing Products or Services

32 Manufacturing enterprises with a share of 44,4% percentage gave the 'always' answer to the variable 'We always add new ones to our existing products and services. With a share of 34,7% there are 25 firms which said 'Often' to this variable. 9 firms preferred the 'Sometimes' option whereas 3 preferred 'never' and 3 preferred 'rarely'.

6.4 Findings Related To Process Innovation of Small and Medium-Sized Manufacturing Enterprises Located in Konya

	Frequency	Percent
Never	0	0,0
Rarely	1	1,3
Sometimes	10	13,9
Often	45	62,5
Always	16	22,2
Total	72	100,0

Table 9 Continuous Improvement Effort in Production Processes

To the variable "We show continuous improvement effort in production processes in our enterprise" from 72 manufacturing firms, 45 manufacturing enterprises replied 'often', while with 22,2% percent share 16 enterprises preferred 'always', 10 preferred 'Sometimes' and 1 preferred 'Rarely' option. No manufacturing enterprises gave the answer 'never' to this variable.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	0	0,0
Rarely	1	1,3
Sometimes	7	9,7
Often	48	66,7
Always	15	20,8
Total	72	100,0

Table 10 Continuous Innovation Making Effort in Service / Product Delivery and Operations

With a 66.7% percent 48 of 72 small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises in Konya preferred the 'often' option of the item: 'We show continuous innovation making Effort in service / product delivery and operations of our enterprise'. With percentage share of 20,8 15 enterprises preferred the 'always' option while 7 enterprises selected 'sometimes' option and 1 firm gave the answer 'rarely'. No manufacturing firms chose the 'never' option.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	0	0,0
Rarely	1	1,3
Sometimes	2	2,8
Often	30	41,7
Always	39	54,1
Total	72	100,0

Table 11 Reviewing the Concept of Market Depending On New Developments

To the variable "We review the concept of market depending on new developments " 39 manufacturing enterprises with a 54,1% percent replied 'always' while 30 enterprises preferred 'often', 2 preferred 'Sometimes' and 1 preferred 'Rarely' option. No manufacturing enterprises gave the answer 'never' to this variable too.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	2	2,8
Rarely	0	0,0
Sometimes	34	47,2
Often	34	47,2
Always	2	2,8
Total	72	100,0

Table 12 Changing Presentation of Existing Products or Delivery of Services to Consumers

34 of 72 manufacturing enterprises examined in this study preferred 'often' option of the item: 'we often change the presentation of existing products or delivery of services to consumers'. With percentage 34 enterprises preferred the 'Sometimes' option while with 2 enterprises preferred 'always' and 2 gave the answer 'never'. No manufacturing firms chose the 'rarely' option.

6.5 Findings Related to Marketing Innovation of Small and Medium-Sized Manufacturing Enterprises Located in Konya

	Frequency	Percent
Never	0	0,0
Rarely	1	1,3
Sometimes	4	5,6
Often	27	37,5
Always	40	55,6
Total	72	100,0

Table 13 Searching the Ways to Find New Needs and Markets

To the variable "We search the ways to find new needs and markets" 40 manufacturing enterprises with a 55,6% percent replied 'always' while 27 enterprises preferred 'often'. 4 enterprises preferred 'Sometimes' and 1 manufacturing enterprise with a 1,3% percent share preferred 'Rarely' option.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	5	6,9
Rarely	7	9,7
Sometimes	34	47,2
Often	26	36,1
Always	0	0,0
Total	72	100,0

Table 14 Continuously Entering a New Product or Service Areas not entered before

With a 47.2% percent 34 manufacturing enterprises the 'sometimes' option for the variable: 'We continuously enter a new product or service areas not entered before'. 26 enterprises preferred the 'often' option while 7 enterprises selected 'rarely' option and 5 manufacturing enterprises gave

the answer 'never'. No manufacturing firms chose the 'always' option.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	0	0,0
Rarely	2	2,8
Sometimes	16	22,2
Often	36	50,0
Always	18	25,0
Total	72	100,0

Table 15 Repositioning Existing Products or Services

With a 50,0% percent 36 of 72 small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises preferred the 'often' option for the item: 'We often reposition our existing products or services'. There are 18 enterprises replied 'always'. With percentage share of 22,2 16 enterprises stated that they sometimes reposition their existing products and services. 2 enterprises selected 'rarely' option and no manufacturing firms chose the 'never' option.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	1	1,3
Rarely	7	9,7
Sometimes	12	16,6
Often	32	44,4
Always	20	27,8
Total	72	100,0

Table 16 Making Innovation in Product and Service Pricing

32 of 72 small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises, which is the sample of the study, often make innovation for product and service pricing. There are 20 enterprises which always makes innovation. 12 enterprises preferred 'sometimes' option, 7 gave the 'rarely' answer and 1 gave the answer 'never'.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	1	1,3
Rarely	0	0,0
Sometimes	2	2,8
Often	41	56,9
Always	28	38,9
Total	72	100,0

Table 17 Reviewing Sales Techniques and Finding New Methods

To the variable "We always review our sales techniques and try to find new methods" 41 manufacturing enterprises with a 56, 9% percent replied 'often' while 28 enterprises preferred the 'always' option. 1 enterprise selected the 'Never' option and 2 manufacturing enterprises preferred the 'sometimes' option. No manufacturing enterprise selected the "rarely" option.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	0	0,0
Rarely	4	5,6
Sometimes	9	12,5
Often	32	44,4
Always	27	37,5
Total	72	100,0

Table 18 Searching for the Ways to Develop Promotion Methods and Tools

To the variable “We always search for the ways to develop our promotion methods and tools” 32 manufacturing enterprises replied 'often', 27 enterprises preferred the 'always' option. 9 enterprises selected the 'Sometimes' option and 4 manufacturing enterprises preferred the 'rarely' option. The answer “never” was not given in this variable.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	2	2,8
Rarely	2	2,8
Sometimes	8	11,1
Often	44	61,1
Always	16	22,2
Total	72	100,0

Table 19 Searching New Ways for Payment Methods of Products and Services

44 of 72 manufacturing enterprises replied the survey stated that they ‘often’ search for new ways for payment methods of products and services. With a 22,2 percentage 16 enterprises pointed out that they ‘always’ do this search. 8 enterprises gave the 'Sometimes' answer while with 2 enterprises preferred 'rarely' option and 2 gave the answer 'never'.

	Frequency	Percent
Sometimes	3	4,1
Often	37	51,3
Always	32	44,4
Total	72	100,0

Table 20. Renewing Production Designs according to Customer Needs and Competing Productions

37 of the 72 sample, with a per cent of 51,3, stated that they “Often” renew their production designs according to customer needs and competing productions, and 32 answered as “Always”. 3 enterprises, which equal to %4,1, answered as “Sometimes”; “Rarely” and “Never” answers were not given.

6.6 Findings about Organizational Innovation in Small and Middle Sized Manufacturing Enterprises in Konya

	Frequency	Percent
Sometimes	11	15,2
Often	23	31,9
Always	38	52,8
Total	72	100,0

Table 21. Finding New Ways to Start and Develop Relations with Customers

For “We try to find new ways of starting and developing relations with the customers” item, 38 manufacturing enterprises, which equal to %52,8, stated as “Always”; 23 answered as “Often” and 11 as “Sometimes”. “Rarely” and “Never” answers were not given.

	Frequency	Percent
Rarely	2	2,8
Sometimes	34	47,2
Often	34	47,2
Always	2	2,8
Total	72	100,0

Table 22. Making Reforms in the Management of Enterprises' Foreign Affairs

34 of 72 stated that they “Often” make reform in managing their foreign affairs and the same number of enterprises stated as “Sometimes” for this item. “Rarely” and “Always” answers were both given by two enterprises; “Never” was not given as an answer.

	Frequency	Frequency
Rarely	2	2,8
Sometimes	29	40,3
Often	39	54,1
Always	2	2,8
Total	72	100,0

Table 23. Making Reforms in Enterprise's Commercial Applications

For the item “We make reforms in our enterprise's commercial applications.”, 39 manufacturing enterprises, which equal to %54,1, stated as “Often” and 29 as “Sometimes”. “Rarely” and “Never” were each stated by 2. “Never” answer was not given for this item.

	Frequency	Percent
Never	2	2,8
Rarely	7	9,7
Sometimes	39	54,1
Often	6	8,3
Always	18	25,0
Total	72	100,0

Table 24. Renewing Job Descriptions in the Enterprise appropriate to Changing Situations

For the item “Job descriptions in our enterprise are continuously renewed appropriate to changing situations.”, 39 of the participants, which equal to 54,1, stated as “Sometimes”. While 18 manufacturing enterprises stated that they “Always” renew the job descriptions, 7 were seen to do this renewal “Rarely”; 2 enterprises stated they “Never” do it.

6.7 The Relationship between Innovation and Enterprise’s Age in Small and Middle Sized Manufacturing Enterprises in Konya

	F	Sig.
Statement 1	,991	,427
Statement 2	2,630	,053
Statement 3	1,253	,310
Statement 4	2,447	,067
Statement 5	2,559	,072
Statement 6	,010	,070
Statement 7	1,447	,242
Statement 8	1,969	,124
Statement 9	1,851	,144
Statement 10	2,547	,059
Statement 11	2,511	,057
Statement 12	1,969	,124
Statement 13	2,113	,101
Statement 14	2,551	,059
Statement 15	1,873	,127
Statement 16	,193	,040
Statement 17	4,025	,093
Statement 18	2,088	,106
Statement 19	3,507	,018
Statement 20	3,479	,119
Statement 21	2,704	,084

Table 25. The Relation of Innovation and Enterprise Age

The data gained by analysis done in order to find

out if there is a meaningful relationship between innovation and enterprise’s age in small and middle sized manufacturing enterprises in Konya shows that there does not exist a meaningful relationship. Since the gained sigma values are greater than 0,05 ($p > 0,05$), H_1 is declined and H_0 is accepted, so the study has presented that there is not a relationship between innovation and enterprise’s age in manufacturing enterprises.

6.8 The Arithmetic of Innovation Types in Small and Middle Sized Manufacturing Enterprises in Konya

	Minimum	Maximum	Value
Production and Service Innovation			
Statement 1	1	5	4,03
Statement 2	2	5	4,03
Statement 3	1	5	4,44
Statement 4	2	5	3,83
Statement 5	2	5	4,17
Process Innovation			
Statement 6	2	5	3,97
Statement 7	2	5	4,03
Statement 8	2	5	4,44
Statement 9	1	5	3,47
Marketing Innovation			
Statement 10	2	5	4,44
Statement 11	1	5	3,06
Statement 12	2	5	3,97
Statement 13	1	5	3,83
Statement 14	1	5	4,28
Statement 15	2	5	4,17
Statement 16	1	5	3,97
Statement 17	3	5	4,39
Organizational Innovation			
Statement 18	3	5	4,39
Statement 19	2	5	3,50
Statement 20	2	5	3,58
Statement 21	1	5	3,42

Table 26. The Arithmetic of Innovation Types

The data shows that prominent type of innovation in manufacturing enterprises is production/service innovation. According to data collected from small and middle sized manufacturing enterprises via the survey we prepared, enterprises “Often” make innovations in their productions/services, so H_1 is accepted and H_0 is declined. The study represents that manufacturing enterprises put production/service innovation into action more often than the other type of innovation.

6. RESULTS

When study results are examined, it is seen that the small and middle sized manufacturing enterprises that function in Konya and have participated this research are generally 6 to 10 years old. The enterprises' per cent with that age in this study equals to %60. As a result of the evaluation of research data, it is seen that there is not a meaningful relationship between enterprise's age and innovation, which means these enterprises are open for reform regardless of their age.

Innovation is seen as to be important and necessary by manufacturing enterprises as understood from the item asking if innovation is important and necessary which got answer "Yes" by all participants. As we highlighted in our study, innovation which is seen as the key in creating an advantage in competition is accepted as a rescuer and a helper to provide superiority by enterprises.

As a result of the research, it is seen that enterprises often pursue developing new productions and services that provide more benefit. Presenting the first example of a production or service in the market is a situation that will provide great superiority.

A frequently seen type of innovation that is seen in manufacturing enterprises is to improve existing products and services. It is debatable if improving only existing products and services is enough in the high level of competition within the market. However, it is clear that the customer asks for more that improvements of existing products and services. Because of this reason, enterprises should not see improvements of products and services enough, but they should add new ones.

As stated in the literature, it is necessary for enterprises to renew themselves continually and adapt this as a kind of culture in order to prolong their lifetime, to get more profit and to be superior within competing enterprises. Innovation made in a single field (e.g. production innovation) will surely provide a contribution to the enterprise, but putting all 4 types of innovation mentioned into action will place the enterprise to the desired position. Doubtlessly, innovation is the fastest means that will take enterprises to the success they have fixed their eyes.

REFERENCES

Afuah, A. (2009). Strategic Innovation, New York: Routledge

Akgemci, Tahir, (2001) "KOBİ'lerin Temel Sorunları ve Sağlanan Destekler", Ankara: Bsm Matbaacılık.

Aygen, S. (2006). İşletmelerde Yenilik Yönetimi Sürecinde Örgüt Yapılarında ve Hizmet Tasarımlarında Yaşanan Dönüşümler: Antalya İli Beş Yıldızlı Konaklama İşletmelerinde Ampirik Bir Araştırma ve Hizmet Tasarımı Önerisi. Yayınlanmamış Doktora Tezi. Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü: Konya

Bayrak, S., Akdiş M. (2000). KOBİ'lerin yönetsel durumu ve sanayileşen illerde analizi, Türkiye Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi, Cilt: 4, Sayı: 1.

Drucker, Peter F. (1985), "The Discipline of Innovation", Harvard Business Review On Point Article, August 2002
<<http://www.engr.pitt.edu/mac/imagest/articles%20and%20docs/DisciplineofInnovation.pdf>> Erişim: Kasım 2012

Elçi, Şirin (2007), İnovasyon Kalkınmanın ve Rekabetin Anahtarı, Ankara: Technopolis Group.

Ersoy, B.A ve Şengül, C.M (2008), "Yenilikçiliğe Yönelik Devlet Uygulamaları ve AB Karşılaştırması", Yönetim ve Ekonomi, 15/1 (2008) 59-74

Göker, Aykut. (2003). "İnovasyonda Yetkinleşmek: Rekabet Üstünlüğüne Giden Yol...", Türkiye'nin Bilim-Teknoloji-İnovasyon Politikası Üzerine İrdelemeler", Ekonomik Yaklaşım Dergisi, Cilt:14, Sayı:47, İstanbul.

Güleş, H.K. ve Bülbül, H. (2004), Yenilikçilik, İşletmelerin Stratejik Rekabet Aracı, Nobel Yayın, 2004, Ankara.

Hantal, Ömer. (2008) "Investigation of the Relations Between SMEs and Main Contractors on the Innovation Management and Innovation Policies", (Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi), İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi, Fen Fakültesi, İstanbul.

Henriksen S. ve Skou P. (2005). Marketing Innovation Scientific Marketing. Journal of Medical Marketing <http://www.nnit.com> Erişim: Kasım 2012

Hjalager, A. M. (2010). A Review of Innovation Research In Tourism. Tourism Management, V: 31, s:2

İmamoğlu, S. (2002). Küçük ve orta ölçekli işletmelerde (KOBİ) yenilik çabaları ve Kobi'lerde ürün yeniliği üzerine bir araştırma. Yayınlanmamış doktora tezi, Gebze İleri Teknoloji Enstitüsü, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.

İraz, R. (2005). Yaratıcılık ve yenilik bağlamında girişimcilik ve KOBİ'ler. Konya: Çizgi Kitabevi.

Johne, Axel. (1999). "Successful Market Innovation", European Journal of Innovation Management, Vol: 2, No: 1, Brussels.

Kiwarı, Rajnish (2008), "Research Project Global Innovation" Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH)
http://www.globalinnovation.net/innovation/Innovation_Definitions.pdf, Eriřim: Kasım 2012

Oslo Kılavuzu (Yenilik verilerinin toplanması ve yorumlanması için ilkeler) (2005). 3. baskı, Ankara: TÜBİTAK

Öğüt Adem, Akgemci Tahir, Şahin Emrah, Kocabacak Ayşe (2007), "İřletmelerde Düşünce Aşamasından Patent Aşamasına Uzanan Süreçte Yenilik Stratejileri ve Buluş Yönetimi"
http://www.sosyalbil.selcuk.edu.tr/sos_mak/makaleler/. Eriřim: Kasım 2012

Özdemir, Şuayıp ve Yusuf Karaca. (2007). "KOBİ'ler İçin Dış Ticaret Yöntemleri ve İhracat Problemleri: Afyon İli Doğal Taş Sektöründe Bir Arařtırma", Ç.Ü. İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi, Cilt 8, Sayı:1, Adana.

Papinniemi, Jorma, (1999). "Creating a Model of Process Innovation for Reengineering of Business and Manufacturing", International Journal of Production Economics, Vol. 60-61, USA.

Schumpeter, Joseph (1934), The Theory of Economic Development, with a new introduction by John E.Elliot, MA:Harvard University Press,Tenth printing, 2004

Şahin, Ayşe, (2009), "Mersin'de Faaliyet Gösteren Küçük ve Orta Büyüklükteki İřletmelerin Yenilik Faaliyetlerinin Ölçülmesi", Doğuş Üniversitesi Dergisi, Cilt:10, Sayı: 2, İstanbul.

Taymaz,Erol (2003), "Teknolojik Yenilik ve Ekonomik Performans",
<<http://www.inovasyon.org/html/kitap.htm>>
Eriřim:Kasım 2012

Üstel,İsmail ve Kabatepe,Erdal (2006),"Kobi'ler ve İnovasyon", Turkab AB-Türkiye İşbirliği Derneği Yayını, Sektörel Görüşler Serisi:4 , Turkab Yayını:18 , Birinci Baskı, Eylül 2006